

Insight Digital Lending pathways
in Italy, Poland and Spain

(i)SDL Insight

Digital Lending pathways
in Italy, Poland and Spain

Report for Spain

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**SDL Insight
Digital Lending pathways in Italy, Poland and Spain
Report for Spain**

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Abstract

During the month of February 2025, FESABID conducted a mass survey involving almost all Spanish libraries. This survey consisted of a questionnaire agreed upon between institutions from Spain (FESABID), Italy (Studio Legale DDA, CLAKP), and Poland (Centrum Cyfrowe), within the framework of the KR21 project, to gather evidence about the position of the library sector regarding the possibility of implementing Secure Digital Lending in their institutions. The results reveal a general lack of awareness of this lending modality, although more than half of responding libraries currently do offer some type of digital loan. In addition, there was a perception of a lack of legislative clarity, as well as not having access to legal or technological advice to support SDL implementation. As a consequence, respondents highlighted a need to improve training and information on SDL in the Spanish library sector.

I. The Context

Article 37 of the Intellectual Property Law in Spain (TRLPI), and specifically points 37.1 and 37.2 (in its consolidated version, subsequent to Royal Legislative Decree 1/1996, of 12 April), protects the ability of libraries to reproduce works without prior authorisation from their authors, as well as to make them available to public users through lending or dedicated terminals. This guarantees compliance with articles 20 and 44 of the Constitution regarding citizens' access to information and culture.

However, Article 40 bis of the same law then limits the scope of Article 37, in order not prevent unjustified harm to the authors of the works and their legitimate right to their exploitation.

SDL (Secure Digital Lending) in Spain must therefore find its place within these limits, between the spaces created by national and EU law, and the protection measures that the industry is capable of applying to digital or digitized works (digital rights management, or DRM). And it will be the GLAM sector (primarily or mainly libraries), who, when the time comes, must successfully implement this lending modality for the benefit of citizens.

But are the actors who will have to carry out SDL in Spain aware of what SDL itself means? What prior knowledge do they have of the concept? Do they have the tools? Do they have the knowledge? What do they think of this digital lending option?

This survey aims to answer all these questions, establishing the situation today, and in particular taking a snapshot of the state of affairs and the perception of SDL in the library sector in Spain.

II. Survey objectives

This survey results from an initiative of Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21) aimed at gathering information from libraries in Spain, Italy, and Poland on (independent) Secure Digital Lending (iSDL). It is a tool to identify, through the responses of sector professionals, obstacles to SDL implementation, including legal, technical, and operational challenges. It will also serve to assess the sector's understanding and perception of this issue, in order to better articulate a way forwards.

III. The Questionnaire

A. Data and Methodology

A.1. Description of the questionnaire and of survey process

A.1.1. Questionnaire Population

A total of 7,640 email addresses were identified for Spanish libraries of all types, including school, national, public, specialised, and more, through information from the Spanish Ministry of Culture's website. This initial figure comprehensively covered virtually all Spanish libraries of all types.

The questionnaire was distributed through two mass mailings, conducted on 5 February 2025, and a reminder on 19 February 2025.

Distribution of the questionnaire was made by FESABID through a licensed software, Brevo, which allows to know the percentage of opened mails, the click-through rate, the hard and soft bounces and its e-mail addresses, and, therefore, to better profile the mailing list for the reminder. As a result, it was possible to calculate a delivery rate of 85.4%, therefore reducing the final number of libraries reached to approximately 6,500 email addresses.

A.1.2. Questionnaire Structure

The survey contained 36 questions, divided into 8 sections. Section 1, focused on the profile of the libraries and professionals answering. The other 7 sections were dedicated to questions concerning SDL issues and questions: section II: digital lending; section III: legal barriers; section IV: technological and infrastructure barriers; section V: risk of

opposition; section VI: human resources; section VII: financial barriers; and section VIII: other issues.

A.2. Numbers of Answers

Questionnaires sent (and received): 6,500

Responses received: 179

=Response rate: 2,75%

B. Results

B.1. Responses to Section I - LIBRARY'S PROFILE

1. For which library are you responding to this questionnaire? (Add the library's name)

See the exhaustive list of responding libraries in appendix II

2. What is your role in the library?

Library technician: 60,9%

Library assistant: 20,1%

Direction: 15,6%

Higher-level role: 3,4%

3. What type of library are you answering for? Following [IFLA's typology](#):

Public libraries: 62,6%
Academic libraries: 20,7%
National libraries: 0,5%
Other libraries: 16,2%

Type of libraries according IFLA's typology

4. What types of collections does your library primarily hold?

1. Monographs
2. Serials
3. Multimedia
4. Digital-only resources
5. Archival material
6. Public domain or out-of-copyright materials
7. Others

Number of libraries reporting holding each item type in their collection

5. What is the size of your library's physical collection?

More than 50% of the participating libraries have a collection of between 10,000 and 50,000 documents

27.4% have between 1,000 and 10,000 documents

More than 18% have a collection exceeding 50,000 documents

And less than 4% of the participating libraries have a collection of fewer than 1,000 documents

Size of library physical collections

6. What is the size of your library's digital collection?

Almost 67% of the libraries have a digital collection of fewer than 1,000 documents.

15% have a digital collection of between 1,000 and 10,000 documents.

6% of the participating libraries have a digital collection of between 10,000 and 50,000 documents.

More than 11% have a digital collection of over than 50,000 documents.

Size of library digital collections

7. Does your library have a dedicated team to manage digital services or collections?

More than 75% of the participating libraries do not have a dedicated team to manage digital collections.

Less than 20% of the participating libraries do have a dedicated team to manage digital collections.

B.2. Responses to Section II - DIGITAL LENDING

8. Does your library provide an e-lending service? [includes questions 8 and 9]

Slightly more than 50% of the participating libraries do offer some type of digital lending. In contrast, 48.6% do not.

Of the libraries that do offer this type of service, almost 39% state that they offer digital lending for all types of resources, while, 54% state that they offer digital lending for a specific type of resource.

10. Does your library digitise physical works and lend digital copies under (i)SDL?

93% of the participating libraries do not perform Secure Digital Lending.

11. If you answer “yes” to the question above, which of the following types of material do you lend under (i)SDL?

Only 6,1% of the libraries offers some kind of SDL
42% of these do so with works in the public domain
5,9% use in-copyright works which are out of commerce
5,9%, use in-copyright works which are on sale but only in paper format
17,6% use in-copyright works which are on sale, also in electronic format
5.9%, other
23.5% don't know

Type of material offered for digital lending using the (i)SDL model

12. Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library's users?

Less than 9% of the participating libraries believe there is a high demand for SDL (Secure Digital Lending), while 50% of the participating libraries state that there is little or no demand.

13. Do you foresee that this demand, in the coming years, will:

31,3% believe it will increase strongly; 29,1% foresee a marginal increase; 17,3% believe it will remain stable; only 1,1% think it will decline, while 21,3% don't know

Forecast demand for SDL

14. In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?

50% of the participating libraries believe that offering SDL in their library is important but not essential. 20% believe it is of little importance, and 22% believe it is an essential service.

B.3. Responses to Section III - LEGAL BARRIERS

15. Does your national copyright law or other legislation authorise (i)SDL, and under what conditions?

12% of the participants have knowledge (to varying degrees) of Spanish copyright laws in relation to SDL. In contrast, more than 88% have no knowledge on this matter.

16. How clear is your country's national copyright law or other legislation regarding (i)SDL?

24% of respondents express the perception that the current copyright legislation is not at all clear regarding SDL, while 20% perceive the law, in this aspect, to be somewhere between 'quite' and 'very' clear. The remaining 56% are unaware of it.

Knowledge of the law regarding SDL and perception of its clarity

B.4. Responses to Section IV - TECHNOLOGICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE BARRIERS

17. What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL?

- 63% of respondents believe that the lack of adequate equipment for digitization is a significant obstacle. Only 12% believe that this factor is not an obstacle.
- 60% of respondents believe that the lack of structure in digital archiving systems is a significant obstacle. Only 7% believe that this factor is not an obstacle.
- 60% of respondents believe that the lack of a technological protection measures system (DRM) is a significant obstacle. 11% believe that this factor is not an obstacle.
- 43% of respondents believe that the lack of knowledge in the field is a significant obstacle. 8% believe that this factor is not an obstacle.

- Those answering 'other' point in their comments to a lack of staff and qualified personnel and a lack of budget as significant obstacles.
- 37% admit a lack of sufficient knowledge to give an opinion.

18. Is your library part of a consortium or collaboration that could share technological resources or infrastructures to enable (i)SDL?

- 59% of respondents report being part of a wider network.

B.5. Responses to Section V - RISK OF OPPOSITION

19. Do you face resistance from within your institution (e.g., staff or administration) to implementing (i)SDL?

- 53% of respondents do not know or have no opinion.
- 32% believe that there are no such internal barriers
- 15% believe that they do exist.

20. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors?

- 61% of respondents do not know or have no opinion.
- 18% do not have such a perception.
- 16% do believe it is an impeding factor.

Is possible legal action holding up adoption of (i)SDL?

21. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential technological barriers?

- 51% of respondents do not know or have no opinion.
- 26% do believe that the technological factor is an impediment, while
- 18% do not believe that this is a factor preventing the implementation of SDL.

22. How would the publishing industry in your country respond to the idea of (i)SDL?

- 40% of respondents do not know or have no opinion.
- 35% believe that publishers would oppose SDL.
- 14% believe that publishers would adopt a neutral position, and
- 11% believe in that publishers would take a favourable stance.

B.6. Responses To Section VI - HUMAN RESOURCES

23. Does your library have access to legal expertise to address copyright and (i)SDL-related issues?

- 63% of respondents state that they do not have access to legal advice in this area.
- 18% of respondents do not know.
- 15% state that they do have this type of advice.

24. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects?

- 77% of respondents state that they have not received any type of training or guidance in this area.
- 12% do not know if such training or guidance has been carried out in their institution.
- 11% state that they have had limited training.

25. Do you think such legal training or guidance is necessary?

- 87% believe that it is necessary.
- 3% do not see it as necessary.
- 11% have no opinion on the matter.

Is legal training necessary?

26. Does your library have access to technological expertise to address (i)SDL-related issues?

- 69% of respondents state that they do not have technological advice in this area.

- 9% state that they do have access to technological advice on issues related to SDL.
- 17% do not know.

27. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's technological aspects (e.g., digital rights management, archiving systems, etc.)?

- 74% of respondents state that they have not received any type of training or guidance in this area.
- 15% state that they have had limited training.
- 11% do not know if such training or guidance has been carried out in their institution.

28. Do you think such technological training or guidance is necessary?

- 87% believe that it is necessary.
- 3% do not see it as necessary.
- 10% have no opinion on the matter.

Is technological training necessary?

B.7. Responses To Section VII - FINANCIAL BARRIERS

29. Does your library have adequate financial resources to implement (i)SDL?

- 72% of respondents state that their center does not have the necessary budget for the implementation of SDL.
- 6% state that they do have the necessary budget.
- 22% do not know.

30. Are digitisation tools and DRM systems affordable for the library?

- 46% state that they do not have access to such tools.
- 8% state that they have such tools.
- 45% do not know.

B.8. Responses To Section VIII – OTHERS

31. Would you or your staff benefit from more information/training events on (i)SDL?

- 83% of respondents believe that it would be beneficial for centers and staff to have more information and/or training on SDL.
- 5% do not see it as necessary.
- 12% have no opinion.

32. In your opinion, what steps should national policymakers take to facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries?

- 43% of respondents believe that and adequate training and financial support would facilitate the adoption of the SDL in libraries.
- 22% have no opinion.
- 12% a clear and adequate legislation.
- 23% suggested other responses.

Main measures to implement SDL

33. Do you think (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries in the future?

- 48% of respondents believe that SDL will become more important as a form of lending in the future.
- 17% believe that it will not acquire greater importance in the future.
- 35% do not know.

34. Could the library's (i)SDL system integrate with existing catalogues and platforms?

- 67% do believe that SDL can be integrated into current catalogs and platforms.
- 1% do not see it as possible.
- 32% do not know.

35. Can the library secure users' personal and digital content data by providing (i)SDL?

- 59% believe that the protection of personal data is compatible with the implementation of SDL, while
- 1% do not see it as compatible.
- 40% do not know.

36. What are the negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL?

- 34% believe that the main negative consequence for users of not implementing SDL is having physically to travel to the library to access documents.
- 24% point to the loss of attractiveness of libraries in terms of the services provided, compared to other digital platforms for accessing cultural content.
- 18% believe that the user and the library lose relationship and interaction links.
- 16% do not know what negative consequences may arise.
- 4% believe that libraries will be subjected to greater social pressure to offer digital access options to cultural content.
- 3% of respondents foresee no negative consequences in the non-implementation of SDL.

C. Summary of Questionnaire's results

C.1. Section I – RESPONDENT LIBRARY PROFILES

Almost 60% of the libraries that responded to the questionnaire are public libraries. These are the libraries that serve the largest user population, but at the same time, in many cases, they are the libraries with the smallest budgets and staffing, especially in terms of technical personnel with legal or technological knowledge.

They also tend to have less autonomy in decision-making regarding how they carry out lending beyond traditional analogue lending, or digital lending based on agreements with publishers. This limited autonomy is explained by their dependence, in many cases, on the decisions of those running the networks of which they form part, be they municipal or supramunicipal.

To this we must add that almost 70% of the libraries that responded state that they have a digital collection of fewer than 1,000 documents, while over half of respondents report physical collections of between 10,000 and 50,000 documents. This lack of experience with digital may well explain the high percentage of 'don't know, no answer' responses to the more specific questions on the legal and technological aspects of Secure Digital Lending.

C.2. Section II - DIGITAL LENDING

Although more than half of the participating libraries do carry out digital lending, almost 93% do not do so under the (independent) Secure Digital Lending model. In most cases, digital lending is carried out through digital lending platforms under licence from publishers, as is the case with the "eBiblio" service, which present in almost the entire country. Catalonia and

the Basque Country have their own electronic lending projects, but they are based on the same "eBiblio" principle.

The documents available for lending under this model depend on those available in the publishers' eBook catalogue. In many cases, these are non-permanent titles, so the exploitation licenses have an expiration date and so need to be renewed. It is also common for the acquisition of these licenses to be done in bulk, not individually, work-by-work.

The few libraries that offer Secure Digital Lending (just over 6% of the responses) do so, for the most part, with works that are already in the public domain, which means that there are no legal impediments to address their public communication, nor expenses associated with the need to apply DRM.

The local profile of most participating libraries (public libraries located in towns and local neighbourhoods), and the fact of already having tools such as interlibrary loan, may mitigate against prioritising models (such as (i)SDL) that bring works closer to users without having to physically go to distant libraries. This may explain the perception of little or no current demand for SDL by more than 50% of the responses, which coincides with the 50% who see SDL as an important but not essential service, and likewise, again 50% who believe that its future demand will remain stable or increase marginally.

C.3. Section III - LEGAL BARRIERS

Only 12% of respondents state that they have knowledge about the legislation related to SDL, while 80% either do not know it or believe it is very unclear in this regard.

C.4. Section IV - TECHNOLOGICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE BARRIERS

3 out of 5 respondents believe that the lack of adequate equipment for digitisation, the lack of structure in digital archiving systems, and the lack of easily applied technological protection measures tools (DRM) are significant obstacles for the implementation of (i)SDL. Closely linked to this are questions around having the budgets and staff not only to buy but then also to operate these tools.

It should be noted nonetheless that almost another 40% admitted a lack of knowledge to give an opinion.

C.5. Section V - RISK OF OPPOSITION

The relative lack of knowledge more broadly about (i)SDL is associated with a low perception of risk or opposition to the implementation of (i)SDL.

53% of respondents do not know if there is or would be opposition from the management of their library or from the management of the consortia or networks on which their institution depends. Meanwhile, over 60% of respondents say that they do not know if libraries would hesitate to implement SDL due to fear of an adverse reaction from the publishing sector.

In the first case, more than 30% believe that there would be no opposition within their own institutions, while the perception that libraries would not opt for SDL due to fear of an adverse reaction from the publishing sector is only shared by 16% of respondents. At the same time, 18% believe that if SDL is not implemented, it would not be for this reason. Paradoxically, almost 35% of respondents do believe that the publishing sector would react negatively to SDL.

These percentages seem to indicate that the library community would not anticipate opposition either from the management of their own institutions or beyond (publishing sector).

C.6. Section VI - HUMAN RESOURCES

The majority of libraries agree about the impact of a lack of human resources, both in number -lack of staffing- and in knowledge (lack of specific training). More than 40% of respondents believe that the lack of knowledge in the field is a significant obstacle.

Likewise, 63% of participating libraries state that they do not have adequate access to advice on legal issues related to SDL, and almost 77% state that they have not received any type of training in this regard.

In contrast, almost 87% state that this type of training in legal aspects would be necessary.

Regarding technological aspects, almost 69% state that they do not have adequate access to advice around the technology needed for SDL, and 75% state that they have not received any type of training in this sense. 87% of respondents state that this training would be necessary.

Overall, there is a consistent message throughout the document of a fairly widespread lack of knowledge of key aspects related to SDL (functional, legal, and technological aspects), but at the same time a demand from the library community for greater investment in specific training on these aspects.

B.7. Section VII - FINANCIAL BARRIERS

In the section on financial obstacles, the responses point in a similar direction as those in the previous section. 72% of libraries state that they do

not have the necessary budget for the implementation of SDL. In contrast, to the more specific question about whether the tools necessary for digitisation and the technological protection of copyright (DRM) are affordable for the library, the percentage of "no" drops to 46%, complemented by 45% of "don't know, no answer".

C.8. Section VIII – OTHERS

In the last section of the survey, the responses show a positive predisposition towards SDL, and strong interest in accessing training events on SDL in the future. More than 83% of respondents express this wish.

But again, when asked about specific measures that should be carried out by politicians, an increase in investment, together with training, accounts for 43% of the responses. Considering that this is a free-text response, this percentage of similar answers is particularly relevant perhaps.

Finally, 47.5% of respondents believe that SDL will become a more important lending model for libraries in the future. The vast majority believe that it will be compatible with current catalogues (67%) and with the safeguarding of users' personal data (59%).

If SDL is not implemented, libraries believe they will lose in attractiveness when it comes to the services and content they can offer, compared to other libraries or digital platforms (24% of respondents believe this). To an even greater extent (34%), they are concerned about the impact on users of not being able to access the cultural content of their library unless they physically travel to the library itself.

D. Conclusions

Currently, only 50% of the participating libraries in the survey offer some type of digital lending. 93% of the participating libraries don't offer SDL.

More than 70% of the participating libraries nonetheless see the importance of offering SDL, but only 22% see it as an essential service at the moment.

Over 88% of respondents have no knowledge about whether current legislation permits SDL, and 24% state that this legislation is not at all clear in that regard. This represents a significant barrier.

More than 72% of participating libraries state that they do not have the adequate budget to implement SDL, but almost 60% of these libraries are integrated into wider networks or consortia. The lack of (trained) staff, adequate equipment, and the appropriate technological infrastructure to guarantee DRM are the other key factors perceived by libraries as obstacles to implementing SDL.

Approximately 70% of the participating libraries state that they do not have access to legal or technological advice to address issues related to SDL, nor have they received training in these areas, despite the fact that more than 87% consider this training necessary.

With all these figures, the conclusion seems clear: a service cannot be offered if it is either unknown or not understood in depth. Perhaps due to this same lack of awareness, the libraries that should be offering it do not perceive it as an essential service. Many also lack the autonomy to offer it, or, if they have it, they do not have the economic resources to implement it, nor the necessary training and information. On the other hand, the very lack of knowledge about SDL and the state of affairs may explain the limited perception of fear towards an adverse reaction from the publishing sector that could block the implementation of SDL in libraries. Therefore, other explanations must be sought for the non-implementation (lack of clarity in the laws, lack of interest from authorities, lack of investment, lack of resources in structures and human resources and more,).

Therefore, it is essential to carry out or encourage informational actions first, and then training, so that librarians, directors, and technicians better understand what SDL is, what benefits it has for all their users, and how it can be implemented in their centers in the future. This coincides with the expressed data regarding the little or no training in legal and/or technological aspects concerning SDL, and the high demand for it, with data showing over 80% acceptance of informational events about SDL, and almost 90% demand for training in legal and technological aspects related to it.

And the effort in providing more training and information should be worthwhile, because almost 50% of the participating libraries believe, to some extent, that SDL will become a more important lending modality in the future, and that this lending modality can be integrated into current platforms and catalogues (60% of respondents believe this), compatible with safeguarding the personal data of users.

In parallel, clarifying the possibility for libraries to carry out (independent) Secure Digital Lending could help address worries and uncertainties, complementing the other steps set out above, and realising the potential of eLending.

Appendix A – Questionnaire

Questionnaire on the barriers to the adoption of (independent) Secure Digital Lending (iSDL): Legal, technical, and operational challenges.

This questionnaire results from an initiative of [Knowledge Rights 21](#) (KR21) aimed at gathering information from libraries in Italy, Poland, and Spain concerning (independent) **Secure Digital Lending (iSDL) — e-lending based on paper books digitised by libraries where some protection measures are adopted to prevent non-legitimate uses (for instance, measures to limitate the lending time, to prevent downloading, etc. often named DRM Digital Rights Management Systems)**¹. It investigates the legal, technical, and other barriers that influence the potential for further adoption of (i)SDL.

The partners of this research project are:

Italy: [STUDIO LEGALE DDA](#); [CLAKP](#) (Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group) dell'IGSG (Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari)/CNR (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche)

Poland: [CENTRUM CYFROWE](#)

Spain: [FESABID](#) (Federación Española de Sociedades de Archivística, Biblioteconomía, Documentación y Museística)

The project explores these issues to lay the groundwork for identifying the key challenges and potential benefits behind (i)SDL implementation. The project outcomes could provide a foundation for future strategies to

¹ E-lending in the (i)SDL model was developed as part of the report *eBooks and Secure Digital Lending in European Libraries* (scheduled for publication in January/February 2025). In detail, e-lending based on the (i)SDL model is characterised by the following features: 1) Loans are made by strictly defined entities - establishments accessible to the public (e.g., libraries) that derive no direct or indirect economic or commercial advantage from their lending activity (requirement for a special case); 2) Lending covers the lending of a digital copy of a book; 3) Loans are made under the one copy - one user model; 4) Lending is carried out in a mimetic (i.e., allowing patrons to download electronic copies of books) or a quasi-mimetic fashion (i.e., allowing the use of electronic copies of books in streaming); 5) Lending is only for a limited period; 6) After the lending period has expired, the user cannot use the e-book; 7) A digital copy of a book must be obtained from a lawful source, but the library can make an electronic copy of a legally obtained copy of a paper book; e-lending under the (i)SDL model gives rise to the right to remuneration (PLR) in line with the Rental and Lending Directive; 8) there is no transfer of data, including personal data of library patrons, to publishers or other third parties.

overcome these obstacles and support the mission of libraries in the digital realm.

The questionnaire is divided into eight sections and contains **36 questions**.

Given the topic's relevance, please take about **20 minutes** to respond to the questionnaire we have prepared.

The deadline for completing the questionnaire is **February 26th, 2025**.

We greatly appreciate your participation in this survey, as your responses will directly contribute to shaping the future of (i)SDL in libraries across Europe.

I. LIBRARY'S PROFILE

1. For which library are you responding to this questionnaire? (Add the library's name)

2. What is your role in the library?

3. What type of library are you answering for? Following [IFLA's typology](#):

- National
- Academic
- Public
- School
- Other

4. What types of collections does your library primarily hold? (Select all that apply)

- Serials (e.g., journals, magazines, periodicals)
- Monographs (e.g., books, reports)
- Archival materials (e.g., manuscripts, historical documents)
- Multimedia (e.g., DVDs, audio recordings, images)
- Digital-only resources (e.g., e-books, databases, online journals)

- Public domain or out-of-copyright materials
- Other (please specify)_____

5. What is the size of your library's physical collection?

- Small (less than 1,000 records)
- Medium (1,000–10,000 records)
- Large (10,000–50,000 records)
- Very large (Over 50,000 records)

6. What is the size of your library's digital collection?

- Small (less than 1,000 records)
- Medium (1,000–10,000 records)
- Large (10,000–50,000 records)
- Very large (Over 50,000 records)

7. Does your library have a dedicated team to manage digital services or collections?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

II.DIGITAL LENDING

8. Does your library provide an e-lending service?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

9. If you answer “yes” to the question above, please specify your library's current digital lending model.

- Digital lending provided for specific resources
- Digital lending fully provided
- I don't know

10. Does your library digitise physical works and lend digital copies under (i)SDL?

- Yes

- No
- I don't know

11. If you answer “yes” to the question above, which of the following types of material do you lend under (i)SDL?

(Select all that apply)

- Public domain works
- In-copyright works which are out of commerce
- In-copyright works which are on sale but only in paper format
- In-copyright works which are on sale, also in electronic format
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

12. Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library's users?

- Yes, there is high demand
- Yes, but the demand is moderate
- Very little demand
- No demand
- I don't know

Please specify your answer

13. Do you foresee that this demand, in the coming years, will:

- Increase strongly
- Increase marginally
- Stay stable
- Decline
- I don't know

14. In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?

- Essential
- Important but not essential
- Not important
- I don't know

Please explain why:

III. LEGAL BARRIERS

15. Does your national copyright law or other legislation authorise (i)SDL, and under what conditions?

16. How clear is your country's national copyright law or other legislation regarding (i)SDL?

- Very clear
- Somewhat clear
- Not clear at all
- I don't know

IV. TECHNOLOGICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE BARRIERS

17. What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL?

(Please rate each barrier on a scale from 0 to 5, where 0=I don't know, 1 = Not a barrier and 5 = Major barrier)

Barrier	0=I don't know	1 (Not a barrier)	2	3	4	5 (Major barrier)
Lack of adequate digitisation equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Lack of an adequate archiving system	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Inadequate digital rights management (DRM) system or lack of technical protection measures know-how	<input type="checkbox"/>					

If you think there are other technological barriers, please indicate them below:

18. Is your library part of a consortium or collaboration that could share technological resources or infrastructures to enable (i)SDL?

- Yes

- No
- I don't know

If you answered Yes, please specify which consortium or collaboration

V. RISK OF OPPOSITION

19. Do you face resistance from within your institution (e.g., staff or administration) to implementing (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, please specify

20. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other (please specify)_____

21. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential technological barriers?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other (please specify)_____

22. How would the publishing industry in your country respond to the idea of (i)SDL?

- Strongly supportive
- Neutral
- Opposed
- I don't know

VI. HUMAN RESOURCES

23. Does your library have access to legal expertise to address copyright and (i)SDL-related issues?

- Yes, we have dedicated legal staff or advisor
- No, we lack the necessary legal support
- Other (please specify)_____
- I don't know

24. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects?

- Yes, extensive training
- Yes, but limited training
- No training has been provided
- In progress
- I don't know

If you answer “No” or “In progress” to the question above, please explain any challenges related to human resources:

25. Do you think such legal training or guidance is necessary?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

26. Does your library have access to technological expertise to address (i)SDL-related issues?

- Yes, we have dedicated staff or advisor
- No, we lack the necessary technological support
- Other (please specify)_____
- I don't know

27. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's technological aspects (e.g., digital rights management, archiving systems, etc.)?

- Yes, extensive training
- Yes, but limited training
- No training has been provided
- In progress
- I don't know

If you answer “No” or “In progress” to the question above, please explain any challenges related to human resources:

28. Do you think such technological training or guidance is necessary?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

VII. FINANCIAL BARRIERS

29. Does your library have adequate financial resources to implement (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

30. Are digitisation tools and DRM systems affordable for the library?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

VIII. OTHER

31. Would you or your staff benefit from more information/formative events on (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

32. In your opinion, what steps should national policymakers take to facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries?

33. Do you think (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries in the future?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Please specify why

34. Could the library's (i)SDL system integrate with existing catalogues and platforms?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

35. Can the library secure users' personal and digital content data by providing (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

36. What are the negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL?
(Select all that apply)

The library loses its relationship with users

The library cannot allow a user to read a book if he/she cannot go to the library personally and the publisher has not provided an e-book version of the book.

Users are less likely to engage with the library's services

The library may face increased pressure to offer digital access options

The library's services become less competitive than other libraries or digital platforms.

There are none

Other (please specify)_____

I don't know

Appendix B – Exhaustive list of libraries answering question 1,
Section I, Library's profile

Biblioteca del Centro de Documentación del Observatorio
Vasco de la Juventud
Biblioteca Pública de Cáceres "A.Rodríguez-
Moñino/M.Brey"
Biblioteca Guillem Clfre de COLonya
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de Bormujos
Biblioteca del Parlamento de Cantabria
Biblioteca Municipal de Cenlle
BIBLIOTECA PUBLICA DE LEON
Biblioteca del Conservatorio Superior de Música "Eduardo
Martínez Torner"
BIBLIOTECA NACHO GARCÍA CARRIÓN
Biblioteca Pública Municipal d'Albaida
Biblioteca "Publica Municipal José Becerril Madueño de
Baza (Granada)
Biblioteca Municipal de Valdilecha
BPM Fuentealbilla
Biblioteca Municipal
BIBLLIOTECA DE ABANILLA
Biblioteca del Complejo Hospitalario Universitario de Toledo
(SESCAM)
Biblioteca Pública l'Olleria
Biblioteca Històrica UV
Biblioteca de Alcampell
Biblioteca Municipal Suárez Picallo de Sada- A Coruña
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de Nigrán
fernando almena
Biblioteca del Parlamento de Andalucía
Biblioteca Pública de Alfafar
Marcel Ayats
Biblioteca Juan Goytisolo del Instituto Cervantes de Tánger
Centro de Magisterio "Virgen de Europa"
BPM San Juan de la Cruz
CRAI Música i arts escèniques (FESMAE - IB)
Red de Bibliotecas de Llíria. Valencia.
Biblioteca de la Universidad de Cantabria
BIBLIOTECA PUBLICA MUNICIPAL FRANCISCO FUNES
Biblioteca Pública de Mérida
Biblioteca de la UCAM
Biblioteca Publica Municipal Puntagorda
Biblioteca Pública Municipal Juan Pablo Forner de Mérida

Biblioteca Pública Municipal "Francisco Gómez-Porro"
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de Tinajo
Biblioteca del Instituto de Estudios Canarios
Biblioteca Pública de Salamanca
Biblioteca de la Universidad Católica de Ávila
Servicio de Biblioteca Universitaria de la UDC
BIBLIOTECA MUNICIPAL NOVÉS
Biblioteca Municipal de Beniarbeig
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de Ribadavia
BPM El Palmar de Troya
BIBLIOTECA PÚBLICA DEL ESTADO EN LEÓN
BPM EL REAL DE SAN VICENTE
B.P.M de Mondariz-Balneario
ALM El Verger
Hospital Universitario de Burgos
Agencia de lectura municipal de As Somozas (A Coruña)
Biblioteca Neus Català
Biblioteca Pública de Sort
Jorge Manrique
Biblioteca Blas Infante (Sevilla)
BIBLIOTECA PÚBLICA DE LODOSA
Biblioteca de la Universidad de Almería
BIB PUBLICA RUIZ EGEA DE LA CAM
Universidad Politecnica. Biblioteca y Documentación Científica
Biblioteca de la Asamblea de Extremadura
Ces Cardenal Cisneros
UNIVERSIDAD DE CANTABRIA
Biblioteca Pública de Ledesma
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de San Sebastián de La Gomera
Biblioteca Virtual del Sistema Sanitario Público de Extremadura
Biblioteca UIC
Biblioteca Col·legi Oficial d'Infermeres i Infermers de Barcelona
Biblioteca General del Gobierno Vasco
EL GRADO
FERNANDO SOLANO
BIBLIOTECA DE VETERINARIA (UCM)
Biblioteca Municipal de Teror
Universidad de Valladolid
BIBLIOTECA PÚBLICA MUNICIPAL DE VEDRA
Biblioteca de la Universidad de Oviedo
Biblioteca Pública de Turégano
Generación del 27 de Los Palacios y Villafranca

Biblioteca Municipal de Ames
R. ACADEMIA DE JURISPRUDENCIA Y LEGISLACION DE
ESPAÑA
Agencia de Lectura Municipal de Salinas
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de Helechosa de los Montes
Escuela Superior de Diseño de Aragón
BIBLIOTECA "JOSÉ MANUEL FRAILE GIL"
Biblioteca de Taramundi
Biblioteca de Extremadura
AGENCIA DE LECTURA EL PERELLÓ
AIDIMME - Instituto Tecnológico
Legebiltzarra / Parlamento Vasco
Biblioteca del Colegio Oficial de Arquitectos de Madrid
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de Tolox "Antonio Canca
Guerra"
Universidad Loyola
Centro de Lectura de Lo Pagán
BPM MAGÁN
Lumbier
BIBLIOTECA MUNICIPAL DE FABERO
Miguel Artigas- Monreal del campo
Antsoain
BIBLIOTECA PÚBLICA MUNICIPAL DE ORGAZ
Biblioteca de Casa Amèrica Catalunya
UNED
BIBLIOTECA MUNICIPAL ALBA DE TORMES
BIBLIOTECA TÉBAR
Biblitoeca de Potries
ANTONIO GARRIDO MORAGA
Biblioteca de Costitx
BIBLIOTECA MUNICIPAL DE MOCEJON
Biblioteca Universidad de Murcia
Biblioteca P.M. Cervantes. Jimena de la Frontera
BPM "Alicia Casado" de Tábara
Biblioteca municipal de el barraco
Biblioteca de Belchite Félix Teira Cubel
Biblioteca pública de Bermillo de Sayago
Biblioteca de San Isidro - Níjar
BPM de Brión
Los Canapés
ESPAZO XOVE DE CHANTADA
Biblioteca José María de Pereda (Peñamellera Baja)
Conservatorio Profesional de Música de Santa Cruz de
Tenerife
Conservatorio Profesional Jesús Guridi (Vitoria-Gasteiz)
Biblioteca pública municipal Dulcinea

Biblioteca Josep Pla
Biblioteca del Centro Cultural Municipal de Sta María la Real de Nieva
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de Peñaranda de Bracamonte
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de Torrijos (Toledo)
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de Miajadas
Biblioteca del Campus de Melilla de la Universidad de Granada
BIBLIOTECA DE L' AUDIÈNCIA PROVINCIAL DE LLEIDA
Biblioteca Sant Agustí
Maria Moliner
Biblioteca Pública Municipal "Joaquín Rodríguez"
Biblioteca Universitaria de Burgos
Archivo-Biblioteca-Hemeroteca Ayuntamiento Zaragoza
Xarxa de Biblioteques Públiques de Dénia
Biblioteca Municipal Central
Ilustre Colegio Notarial de Valencia
Biblioteca San Ildefonso
Universitat Oberta de Catalunya
Biblioteca Pública del Estado en Cáceres A.Rodríguez
Moñino/M. Brey
Biblioteca de la Asamblea Regional de Murcia
Real Academia de Medicina y Cirugía de Valladolid
Biblioteca del Archivo Histórico Municipal de Ciutadella
Biblioteca i Centre de documentació IVAM
Biblioteca Publica Municipal de Yeles
Biblioteca Pública Municipal " Tomás de Iriarte" Puerto de la Cruz.
Biblioteca Histórica Municipal (Ayuntamiento de Valencia)
Biblioteca Universidad Eclesiástica San Dámaso
Biblioteca Municipal "Doña Pilar" (Zaratán)
Biblioteca Pública Municipal
BIBLIOTECA MUNICIPAL PEDRO DE LORENZO
Biblioteca alar del rey
Biblioteca Juan Régulo Pérez (Federación Española de Esperanto)
Biblioteca Pública Municipal Gómez Sara. Fuente del Maestre (Badajoz)
Especializada de archivo
Fundació Mallorca Literària
Biblioteca de la Universidad Pública de Navarra
Agencia de Lectura Pública Municipal
Biblioteca Central Educativa Consejería de Educación y Formación Profesional Región de Murcia
BIBLIORECA PÚBLICA MUNICIPAL BURJASSOT
Biblioteca Municipal "Feliciano Gracia" de Gallur

Biblioteca de la Real Escuela Superior de Arte Dramático
Biblioteca Universitaria San Pablo-CEU
Biblioteca de Técnicas Reunidas
Universidad Pontificia Comillas
Almudena Grandes Cercedilla
Sección de Documentación de la Consejería de Política
Social, Familias e Igualdad
Biblioteca Municipal "Agustín Ramírez Alemán"
Biblioteca Pública Municipal de Capdepera
Biblioteca Adolfo Bioy Casares del Instituto Cervantes de El
Cairo
Biblioteca Tribunal Superior de Justicia de Madrid
Biblioteca de Investigación del Archivo Municipal de Vitoria-
Gasteiz "Pilar Aróstegui"
Facultat de Comunicació i Relacions Internacionals
Blanquerna (Universitat Ramon Llull)
Biblioteca del Círculo de Amistad XII de Enero
Biblioteca Municipal Central S/C de Tfe
BIBLIOTECA PÚBLICA MUNICIPAL DE VILLANUEVA DEL
REY
Biblioteca Pública Insular d'Eivissa
Biblioteca Canyadó i Casagemes - Joan Argenté
Biblioteca Volpelleres Miquel Batllori

Appendix C – Excerpt of the most significant free-text comments

1. Regarding question 12 of the questionnaire, (*Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library's users?*) one respondent, a public library director, stated:

“When that possibility is offered, I estimate there will be considerable demand.”

2. Regarding question 17 of the questionnaire (*What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL?*), a respondent, director of a university library, opines:

“Each publisher chooses a different way to lend their electronic books, and it is not possible to implement them all efficiently.”

3. Regarding question 20 of the questionnaire (*In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors?*), a respondent, service manager at the documentation center of an art museum, responds:

“If it is carried out within the law, there is no reason to fear a negative reaction from publishers, authors, or copyright management societies.”

4. In the comments related to question 24 of the questionnaire (*Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects?*), a respondent, an assistant technician in a public library, states that they have not received any type of training, and requests:

“Courses and training should be planned (both for people who have just started and for those who have been working for years).”

5. Regarding question 32 of the questionnaire (*In your opinion, what steps should national policymakers take to facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries?*), a respondent, a librarian in a public library, states the following:

fesabid

Knowledge
Rights
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“All necessary measures: from the payment of licenses to legal advice, courses and training, etc.”